

The Meaning of Life Inside Our Evolutionary Human Brain: The Clash of Understanding in Allahless Universe between the Scientific Worldview and the Islamic Worldview

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Abstract: Why am I here? What is the meaning of my life? What is the purpose of my existence? These are the philosophical questions answered by theologians, religious figures and philosophers. For thousands of years, we have found those questions' answers through religious teaching and philosophy. However, due to advent of New Atheism, these questions are snatched by the proponents of scientific worldview. Islam and other religions are fundamentally wrong and no truth at all fundamentally. Since religions are human projection, scientific worldview should intervene those questions and try to formulate those answers from scientific paradigm. The problem is the existential crisis may occur in Muslim minds when they are newly introduced with scientific worldview. This research uses qualitative methodology. This research finds that there is serious clash for answer on the question about the meaning of our life between the scientific worldview and the Islamic worldview. Islamic worldview suggests the meaning of life which is centralized with Allah's existence whereas the scientific worldview suggests the meaning of life with the insignificance of our existence in the vast evolutionary universe at the absence of transcendental reality.

Keywords: The Meaning of Life, Purpose of Existence, Islamic Worldview, Scientific Worldview, New Atheism, Existence of Allah, Pessimism, Nihilism, Optimism, Salman Rushdie, Anton Chekhov, Mahatma Gandhi, Leo Tolstoy, Non-existence of Allah, Why am I here?.

1. Introduction

This circle within which we come and go
Has neither origin nor final end.
Will no one ever tell us truthfully
Whence we have come, and whither do we go?
...

The heavenly bodies that circle round the skies
Are full of mystery even to learned men;
Hold firm the thread of wisdom in your hand,
For those who plan their lives will be confused [1].

Muslim Medieval scientist and poet Umar Khayyam uttered these words through his poetry. Did Umar Khayyam realize that

something is fishy with Islamic and other religious teaching about our human existence on this planet? Did all prophets and early sages lie against the existence of God? Is it like no external deity like Allah/Vogoban/God caused our existence? Obviously, Khayyam was medieval scientist, and he was not unaware of scientific worldview like 20th or 21st century scientist. Even Darwin and Einstein's thought, we have observed the tendency of agnosticism. Only new atheism comes with strong advocacy for none-existence of transcendental reality (Allah).

In mystic literature, our universe and we, species of this planet, are product of existential waves like Ocean wave. Scientific Worldview came and challenge entire religious and mystic literature about given divine purpose or meaning of life. We humans create meaning of life through religious teaching. Allah/God/Vogoban has created us. It provides nice consolation. Is not it? The purpose of life is to worship God and satisfy him to enter heavenly garden. Unfortunately, all are lies and nothing more than human projections. That is the clear-cut message of the scientific worldview.

The scientific literature describes how humans come to this point from the process of evolution from other species over 4.5 billion years. The early chemical evolution for millions of years perhaps led to biological evolution. Our known universe also follows same pattern of evolution for 13.5 billion years. Hence, the question of the meaning of life is absurd in scientific worldview. Our universe and our lives are ultimately purposeless and meaningless. Albert Camus called it as life of absurdity, and we need to deal with absurdity so long we are alive.

At least meaning of life question was not concerned for science for last 2 thousand years. The religion and philosophy tried to answer the question. With the advent of New Atheism, the tendency seems changed in 21st century. After the Kant's introduction of categorical imperative or even in last century for

the development in psychology we never thought this question comes into the area of science. The evolutionary psychology comes in, and now the trend to describe morality or ethics or religious beliefs or meaning and purpose of existence. All are covered or snatched by scientific worldview. Christopher Hitchens, Sam Harris, Richard Dawkins or Daniel Dennett all discussed about morality, ethics and purpose of life under the framework of scientific worldview. Sam Harris work can be referred at this instance [2]. This is quite thought-provoking because we normally put these questions with moral philosophy or ethics or religious philosophy or ethics. This is completely new introduction for scientific worldview. It is not like Dostoevsky's concept if Allah does not exist, everything is allowed. Morality was very ambiguous topic after Darwin Nietzsche tried to introduce new morality and ethics in Godless world, but scientific worldview introduces new morality and ethics based on scientific advancement and evolution of ethical values. Due to our education, we are being more civilized. The secular ethics seems promoting humanism. The foundation is no longer standing on religion or philosophy, rather kind of evolutionary process of our species. For example, imagine a place in which there was no people. Government of that country decided to build buildings. As buildings are constructed and people are given that place to live. We see so many things happening around that area. There is no miracle in it. Similarly, when our ancestors were in constant battle in jungle, they have tendency to develop violence mentality, but as they slowly invent so many ways to survive, they try to modify and be more civilized. That is why despite having evolutionary mindset of violence, we cause less violence due to our advanced adaptive knowledge.

This research, however, will confine and deal with basic existential questions e.g. what is the meaning of our life? or What is the purpose of our existence? or why am I here? The scientific worldview and the Islamic worldview both answer the question. However, the problem is scientific worldview completely negates the answer from Islamic worldview. This polarization of two worldviews urge to produce this research paper. The existential crisis may happen for Muslim youths as well as world youths at initial stage of investigation when they study the books on New Atheism and Islamic worldview. This research is qualitative. The data has been collected from internet sources and library research has been done as well.

2. The Scientific Worldview and the Islamic Worldview on the Meaning of Life

"I am a fool with a heart but no brains, and you are a fool with brains but no heart; and we're both unhappy, and we both suffer." – Fyodor Dostoevsky, *The Idiot* [3].

19th century is the very starting point of pessimistic literature due to the scientific worldview in Western World. The credit goes to Darwin for sure. Other version of theories did not shake the myth of theology in Abrahamic beliefs than evolutionary concept of Darwin. Another Russian Writer, Chekhov, spoke thus in his short story through the character of a professor of science.

Unfortunately, I am not a philosopher and not a theologian

...Just as twenty, thirty years ago, so now, on the threshold of death, I am interested in nothing but science. As I yield up my last breath I shall still believe that science is the most important, the most splendid, the most essential thing in the life of man; that it always has been and will be the highest manifestation of love, and that only by means of it will man conquer himself and nature...In the middle of my lecture tears suddenly rise in my throat, my eyes begin to smart, and I feel a passionate, hysterical desire to stretch out my hands before me and break into loud lamentation. I want to cry out in a loud voice that I, a famous man, have been sentenced by fate to the death penalty, that within some six months another man will be in control here in the lecture-theatre. I want to shriek that I am poisoned; new ideas such as I have not known before have poisoned the last days of my life, and are still stinging my brain like mosquitoes. And at that moment my position seems to me so awful that I want all my listeners to be horrified, to leap up from their seats and to rush in panic terror, with desperate screams, to the exit. It is not easy to get through such moments [4].

Allah never existed, exist or will exist from scientific worldview. Imagine a Muslim boy who grew up learning with firm conviction that Allah exists and there is no doubt about it. Scientific Worldview rejects that very truth conviction of this Muslim youth. If he really studied well, he has no option but to re-examine scientific worldview. Though he desperately tries to believe and make all logical arguments and deep down he realizes that he is doing nothing but lying out of his personal Ego. The sophistry is there. He cries alone as a consequence. Allah is dead. Nihilism or extreme pessimism is there at this initial realization. The feeling is like yesterday your favourite sports car was taken by government agency and you wake up thinking your car is in your garage and suddenly you realized government legally stole your car forever. Scientific worldview, thus, killed Abrahamic Allah which was very last hope for billion of Jews, Christians and Muslims. The majority of world population was filled up by these people. Muslim youths were quite unaware of that fact. E.g. When Salman Rushdi's book was banned, very few people read that book among Muslims. In fact, Salman Rushdi's Islamophobic attitude was due to scientific worldview and very few Muslim students notice those inherent contradiction because most were busy with blasphemy issue. Rushdi states:

"Ha! Ha! Yes, sir, you could say. A humble foot soldier, sir, in the army of Guard Almighty." Oh, almighty guard, why didn't you say. "I am a man of science, sir, and it has been my mission, my mission and let me add my privilege, to visit your great nation to do battle with the most pernicious devilment ever got folks' brains by the balls." "I don't follow." Dumsday lowered his voice. "I'm talking monkey-crap here, sir. Darwinism. The evolutionary heresy of Mr. Charles Darwin." His tones made it plain that the name of anguished, God-ridden Darwin was as distasteful as that of any other fork-tail fiend, Beelzebub, Asmodeus or Lucifer himself. "I have been warning your fellow-men," Dumsday confided, "against Mr. Darwin and his works. With the assistance of my personal fifty-seven-slide presentation. I spoke most recently, sir, at the World Understanding Day banquet of the Rotary Club, Cochinchina."

Kerala. I spoke of my own country, of its young people. I see them lost, sir. The young people of America: I see them in their despair, turning to narcotics, even, for I'm a plain-speaking man, to premarital sexual relations. And I said this then and I say it now to you. If I believed my great-granddaddy was a chimpanzee, why, I'd be pretty depressed myself." [5]

Rushdie was not wrong, and he realized the inherent problem with scientific worldview. Muslim youths are yet to realize but the problem of anger and frustration will not be due for long. I quoted and said thus in Muktomona blog relating faith of an upcoming Muslim youth on existence of Allah after realizing scientific worldview.

Recently Yuval Noah Harari was supporting Israel and I read his book "Sapiens: A Brief History of Humankind". He knows that God does not exist, and his clan is based on imaginative mind as he described, he still supports Israel. You need to understand what is Arab tribalism looked like in the past. Even if my tribe is wrong, I will still support and die for my clan. This intense emotion is like Charles Dicken's famous novel "Great Expectation" in which Pip, the protagonist uttered, "I loved her against reason, against promise, against peace, against hope, against happiness, against all discouragement that could be." That means this support got nothing to do with the atheism that Richard Dawkins was trying to tell his readers. Richard Dawkin always tries to say that he loves literature, and it makes him cry whenever he reads it; but it got nothing to the literature that universe has presented to us with the clear evidences that can be tested empirically [6].

After recent Palestine-Israel war, one of newly appointed Indian assistant professor in Engineering from Singapore was speaking about Western dominance of definition and manipulation of narratives. He was trying to claim that scientific worldview is nothing more than western control of narrative. Again, I stressed this point. Scientific worldview is greatly different than any other religious beliefs and ideologies. New Atheism is quite strong variant of scientific worldview. This variant is not like New Age Movement or any other movement. Scientific worldview had basis in natural philosophy starting from Thales to some extent. He for the first time tried to explain how our universe could work naturally without any divine intervention. Western philosophy has contributed to scientific worldview, yet over 2000 years we never saw such trend. Hawking in his book, "The Grand Design" discussed about latest development of M theory as different reality than we experience [7], yet all the contribution goes to explain universe without divine or mystic explanation. The existential waves are coming from nothing as multiverses and no mystical explanation from absolute and mystery of mysteries work here. Quantum physics is definitely works as mysticism of science. Yet New atheism describe it not from perspective of New Age movement rather the poetry of science is taken for granted towards non-existence of Allah. Quran states,

"I did not create jinn and humans except to worship Me." [8] Also Quran states,

"Say, "Surely my prayer, my sacrifice, my life, and my death are all for Allah—Lord of all worlds." [9]

The meaning and purpose of life is clearly defined by Allah for whole of humanity. There was no issue for Muslims, and they never gave 2nd thought on the existence of Allah. Over 1400 years the belief was unshakable for Islam. The existence of Allah is deeply installed with every Muslim. Scientific Worldview for the first time attacked in a way, there needs 2nd thought on the fundamental doctrine of Islam. Christian and Jews Academicians are perhaps tired of this topic in Western Academia over last 100 years as we have witnessed so many papers on this topic. Muslim scholars produce little on the topic compared to Western academicians. Even they refer this fundamental doctrine, they try to bypass the topic on existence of Allah. In this age of ultra-pragmatism, obviously it does not matter weather Allah exists or not and nobody cares the topic so long people have job and they can survive, marry and live happy life with kids. Praying in Jumma, Eid and having delicious foods with family makes people feel great. Hence, weather Allah exists or not, who cares? There are some dawah organization, let them deal with those topics and these are nothing but religious business enterprise like other business enterprise in market. The country that claims 90% Muslims, the few people are visible in Fajar prayer. The belief is not serious. The prayer for 5 times compulsory for every Muslim, who cares except old people? Like Kierkegaard distinction on the tendency of religiosity in life, we have seen same trend almost in every religion. Only when you grow old, you tend to be religious. The psychology works in same way. Is that the function of evolutionary brain? There is nothing new about it. The problem of boredom is there. The meaninglessness is there. As Camus states, "ONE MUST IMAGINE SISYPHUS HAPPY" [10] Camus dealt with the problem of suicide as thus, "The literal meaning of life is whatever you're doing that prevents you from killing yourself." [11]

Fig. 1. Sisyphus carrying bolder as eternal punishment
Photo Credit: <https://www.peabodylibrary.org/freeforall/?p=6998>

Mainlander in late 19th century could not deal with the problem of suicide after Darwinian revelation. Nietzsche was in sudden shock and hurried up to create new morality in Godless world. Let's look at early reflection on Nietzsche when he mimicked Diogenes of Sinope (l. c. 404-323 BCE) who was the best known for holding a lantern.

A. *The Parable of the Madman*

Have you not heard of that madman who lit a lantern in the bright morning hours, ran to the market-place, and cried

incessantly: "I am looking for God! I am looking for God!"

As many of those who did not believe in God were standing together there, he excited considerable laughter. Have you lost him, then? said one. Did he lose his way like a child? said another. Or is he hiding? Is he afraid of us? Has he gone on a voyage? or emigrated? Thus, they shouted and laughed. The madman sprang into their midst and pierced them with his glances.

"Where has God gone?" he cried. "I shall tell you. We have killed him - you and I. We are his murderers. But how have we done this? How were we able to drink up the sea? Who gave us the sponge to wipe away the entire horizon? What did we do when we unchained the earth from its sun? Whither is it moving now? Whither are we moving now? Away from all suns? Are we not perpetually falling? Backward, sideward, forward, in all directions? Is there any up or down left? Are we not straying as through an infinite nothing? Do we not feel the breath of empty space? Has it not become colder? Is it not more and more night coming on all the time? Must not lanterns be lit in the morning? Do we not hear anything yet of the noise of the gravediggers who are burying God? Do we not smell anything yet of God's decomposition? Gods too decompose. God is dead. God remains dead. And we have killed him. How shall we, murderers of all murderers, console ourselves? That which was the holiest and mightiest of all that the world has yet possessed has bled to death under our knives. Who will wipe this blood off us? With what water could we purify ourselves? What festivals of atonement, what sacred games shall we need to invent? Is not the greatness of this deed too great for us? Must we not ourselves become gods simply to be worthy of it? There has never been a greater deed; and whosoever shall be born after us - for the sake of this deed he shall be part of a higher history than all history hitherto."

Here the madman fell silent and again regarded his listeners; and they too were silent and stared at him in astonishment. At last he threw his lantern to the ground, and it broke and went out. "I have come too early," he said then; "my time has not come yet. The tremendous event is still on its way, still travelling - it has not yet reached the ears of men. Lightning and thunder require time, the light of the stars requires time, deeds require time even after they are done, before they can be seen and heard. This deed is still more distant from them than the distant stars - and yet they have done it themselves."

It has been further related that on that same day the madman entered divers churches and there sang a requiem. Led out and quietened, he is said to have retorted each time: "what are these churches now if they are not the tombs and sepulchers of God?" [12].

Returning in current status quo, what would be answer for the meaning of life then for New Atheism in 21st century. Dawkins states about biological meaning, "Humans have always wondered about the meaning of life... life has no higher purpose than to perpetuate the survival of DNA... life has no design, no purpose, no evil and no good, nothing but blind pitiless indifference." [13]

Krauss states the meaning of life as a theoretical physicist, "If the universe doesn't care about us and if we're an accident in

a remote corner of the universe, in some sense it makes us more precious. The meaning in our lives is provided by us; we provide our own meaning." [14] He also mentions on this topic as thus, "I've told you two things: First, you're much more insignificant than you ever imagined and second, the future is miserable. But you should be happy, because we may live in a universe without purpose but that means the purpose in our lives is the purpose we create. And we should consider ourselves fortunate to have evolved in this place in the middle of nowhere and evolved a consciousness so we can understand the universe from the earliest moments of the big bang to the far future. So instead of being depressed, you should enjoy your brief moment in the sun." [15]

How does Hawking advice for upcoming youths for the world? "Remember to look up at the stars and not down at your feet. Try to make sense of what you see and wonder about what makes the universe exist. Be curious. And however difficult life may seem, there is always something you can do and succeed at. It matters that you don't just give up." [16]

We can observe the evolution of thought on the question of the meaning of life in scientific worldview. Islamic Worldview offers the meaning of life within centralized system that revolves around Tawhid. Hence, One curious Muslim youth and One curious religionless youth can observe the same sky, but one sees the beauty of universe from the Tawhidic paradigm and another observes the beauty of universe from scientific paradigm. Both youths would be lost in time and millions of years both are forgotten, maybe by that time our solar system will pass few galactic years.

Fig. 2. Have you ever thought or imagined a universe without you and Allah after 1 billion years? Muslim youths may not but youths with scientific worldview do imagine in that sort of universe

Source: <https://www.peakpx.com/en/hd-wallpaper-desktop-ngoic>

My uncle, Shoeb Ali who is a science teacher in high school, wrote a lyric for a song. He is a singer after all. He wrote one interesting existential song based on time and our universe,

'Ei Prithibi Vanga Gora Khela Ghore

Itihaas Roche Jai Chatim Vore...

Din guli Haai Kaaler Srote

Veshe Jai Kon Ojanai? Kon Ojanai?"

[Translation: This planet earth is a playhouse of breaking and building

History (world literature) is being written continuously...
Days (of our lives) alas with the stream of time, are floating
away in which unknown mysterious direction?]

Fig. 3. The Question, why am I here? is an existential question
Source: <https://www.psychologytoday.com/gb/blog/authentic-engagement/201707/who-am-i-and-why-am-i-here>

In recent conversation on Nas Daily YouTube Channel, Harari was saying in deep down everyone is an atheist in thought but they simply do not express due to societal pressure and other issues. Harari complained against religions how religions do not encourage students for free inquiry about our universe [17]. Nature is the book and scientists allow mistakes, but religion pretend to be mistakes free and try to have monopoly over knowledge. In earlier video on Atheism in Nas Daily Harari described how has atheism provided him new way looking at the Universe [18]. He grew up in Jews land in Israel where is the birthplace for Abrahamic Monotheistic God. The meaning of life is defined by atheist professor in the state of Israel which is more appealing than jews teaching. What about the case in the Muslim lands?

3. Introspection on Islamic Worldview and Scientific Worldview

Men are obsessed with sex and women are obsessed with marriage. That's what psychology tells us. There are more ants than humans in this planet. In each of their colony, Queen ant leads the way. If somehow queen dies, all will die eventually. Bee has same problem with their evolutionary brain. No philosopher like Jean Paul Sarte came to tell them that there are thousand of alternatives. Scientific determinism stops that hope though. The humans became superior over other species when they broke that obsessed evolutionary psychology. Our usages of intellectual power makes us distinguish from them. Who knows perhaps so many animals look at night sky and thought about their existence and again they become busy with focusing food and sex. The fairy tales maybe right that we read at our childhood among themselves. We human can talk. That gives us key to success. We often notice a beautiful girl is dating with average boy. No secret here except obsessive talking. There are other factors like money and reputation work. The most important thing is talking. The talking got magic in evolutionary brain. Stephen Hawking states, "For millions of years, mankind lived just like the animals. Then something happened which unleashed the power of our imagination. We learned to talk and we learned to listen. Speech has allowed the

communication of ideas, enabling human beings to work together to build the impossible. Mankind's greatest achievements have come about by talking, and its greatest failures by not talking. It doesn't have to be like this. Our greatest hopes could become reality in the future. With the technology at our disposal, the possibilities are unbounded. All we need to do is make sure we keep talking." [19]

Over hundred years psychology has developed enormously. Hence, introspective method was questioned at the middle of 20th century when Behaviorism came into psychology perhaps. The point of scientific worldview and Islamic worldview is indeed very vast area. I [Maruf] cannot understand when I became attached with these two broad areas. Ghandhi wrote autobiography and it was his personal encounter with truth about his world. Everyone has right to belief whatever they wish to belief [20]. I have no problem with it. Gandhi was a vegetarian and he tried to promote non-violence in his teaching. He believed in God and died perhaps with religious belief. Is identity crisis leading to existential crisis? Psychology is weird to me still because no matter what scientific worldview I talk about, I know I will be fallen into category with sexuality or personal suffering or hardship in my personal life. That's how Richard Dawkin's God Delusion was negated as I talked in Muktomona platform. No doubt I face racism, I face so many discriminations and I work like hell day and night like machine at my degree. I read American literature, especially Ernest Hemingway and Robert Frost. Until my final year in English Literature degree, I never thought about the concept that God does not exist. I still remember the presentation when I had to utter that due to scientific enlightenment in Europe, pessimistic literature came into existence in modern literature. There were other factors no doubt but I, somehow, changed my department in Usul Al-Din and Comparative Religion. Initially, I studied all world religious scriptures. I read western philosophy. I read Islamic philosophy. My master thesis allowed me to encounter basic foundation of scientific worldview along with course works. Towards last of my master and in my PhD, I start reading works of Muktomona. Avijit Roy was the strongest voice among them. I read his works. His works are voluminous since he edited and wrote number of books. He was from most prestigious and most competitive engineering public university of Bangladesh (BUET). He did his PhD from Singapore. His arguments were quite persuasive with references. When I started to read his works, I was puzzled why he was killed at the first place because he speaks with full of references. What he speaks, he just translates what western world already faced in last 100 years. West have encountered the scientific worldview. I had to write blog supporting Avijit Roy's works in Muktomona [21]. Earlier I read western philosophy in English and learned scientific worldview reading in English, but reading in Bengali it gave me more comprehensive ability to grasp the area. In my early childhood, I memorized 6 chapters of Quran in Madrasah which helped me later in life to understand how psychology of religious people work. I personally observe all sections of Muslims in Bangladesh. In Malaysia, I participated seminar and conferences during my university education for

last 1 decade. It allows me to compare and contrast ideologies and beliefs. I am a book worm student for last 3 years. I used to climb mountains and rooftops and I walked 100 km mountainous highway in my degree with friends. I had opportunity to explore things with my friends from various countries. I worked part time along the way to mix up with general workers. The normal conversation I observe among them. I did scuba diving, snorkling while working in Tioman Island for 3 months during Covid Lockdown. In other words, I lead my life the way I love. When we talk about the meaning of life or purpose of existence, it is actually introspective one to me. However, I notice scientific worldview forced to push the boundary in recent times as we read works of four horsemen. The world we imagine with religious worldview no longer exist. The problem to me is older generations are simply do not understand. The entire case of Islamization is standing up on sophistry when encountering with scientific worldview. The pragmatism is the most preferable way now in educational curriculum as I understand. I maybe wrong, but I do think we are missing something. My master thesis was based on pragmatism though I did not refer that word. The problem with William James is pragmatism works perfectly like Newtonian physics. However, if anything reaches in the speed of light, Einstein comes into business. In other words, the basis of pragmatism is nothing but lie and false basis. This is the starting point of scientific worldview. Very few academicians take the issue seriously thinking it will be lost in their strong political voice. Scientific worldview does not work in that way. The ideology course I took I feel like the lecturer simply cannot comprehend what do they talk or how dangerous scientific worldview can be for Muslim youths. I do feel like unlike other ideology or worldview, Scientific worldview has very strong grip because it is highly sceptic about every claim about divinity.

I usually walk alone or group in morning and afternoon in jungle nearby female stadium at our Gombak Campus. It came to my mind today while I was walking. One famous Islamic preacher, Delwar Hossain Saidi, gave an example of flower and butterfly. God did not give responsibility to bad looking insects. That is intelligent design. This is confusing how nature was so adaptive to create such beauty as if nature has consciousness. Everything is conscious in this universe since all are active in fundamental level. Scientific worldview challenged such intelligent design to negate existence of Allah from every single sphere of creation. This is not easy task because almost every human got fascinated by the works of nature. The fruits and the flowers and the animals. Such a wonderful planet has been turned into Allahless in scientific worldview. This is called bravery or stubbornness I am really confused sometimes. Our brain is belief making machine and we love to believe because belief makes us lazy and positive about life and universe. Scientists love to challenge and do inquiry but negating the very existence of Allah. This was from scientific worldview. I think most of science or engineering students love to stick to with religion and beliefs, but these beliefs are seen as developed in evolutionary psychology in Human brain. Hence, there is nothing wrong with them pragmatically. Again, it is like we are

limiting with Newtonian physics. Most-modern development makes truth relative. What is true to yourself may not be true to myself. This simple strategy makes us impossible to reach near truth. Whatever the case New Atheism is always on the side that to create this universe, no divine intervention is necessary. If I never read those works, I will never be convinced, and I can be happy with my belief. This is one way but if you want to challenge your worldview and experiment the truth that you hold as absolute truth, then as a seeker of knowledge, we must experiment like Ghandhi and Leo Tolstoy. Maybe they were wrong to understand and accept scientific worldview leaving their religious beliefs, but I do see them sincere at some point. I wish a death of Leo Tolstoy and I wish a life of a farmer like Leo Tolstoy. I hate academia so much sometimes. Yet I decided to be here because maybe I can challenge myself and force myself to understand the universe more dangerously. I love challenge after all. I do not like to lead any lazy life. That's not in Bengali gene as Kazi Nazrul Islam taught us. So, the meaning and purpose of my existence is I do not know for now. I prefer to be in library and read. That's all makes my life meaningful at this stage of my life.

Regarding Islamic Worldview, I have so much to tell since I grew up with this belief in sincerity, yet I pause because as soon as I try to advocate Islam. It feels like I am being observed as insincere. Scientists can study and interpret my worldview in various ways. Islamic Epistemology is not depended on modern epistemology. Introspective messages are there. It is surprising to look at suplications of earlier prophets.

Quran says,

“Say, ‘O Prophet,’ ‘If the ocean were ink for ‘writing’ the Words of my Lord, it would certainly run out before the Words of my Lord were finished, even if We refilled it with its equal.” [22]

Another verse states,

“With Him are the keys of the unseen—no one knows them except Him. And He knows what is in the land and sea. Not even a leaf falls without His knowledge, nor a grain in the darkness of the earth or anything—green or dry—but is ‘written’ in a perfect Record.” [23]

Quran clearly defends the platonic love and existence of Allah as Real. This love that prophet talks about not for beautiful women, world or other things, rather for Allah himself. The scientific worldview discredit the divinity for natural world at the first place. The beauty that we have associated with the creation of Allah for thousands of years is now turned down with self-creation of nature. Quran states,

“Then which of your Lord’s favours will you both deny?” [24]

Not only favours of Lord. Scientific Worldview rejected the very possibility of the existence of God as we have seen in the works of New Atheism.

In 1910, at the age of 82, suddenly during snowfall at night Leo Tolstoy disappeared from his home. Later, he was found death in railway station. In the preface of Suhrawardy’s book, ‘The Sayings of Prophet Muhammad’ it states about Tolstoy’s very last walk on this planet, “I am told by a nephew of mine on the authority of one of his daughters whom he had met in

Russia that a copy of this book was found in the large overcoat in which he had wrapped himself before setting out on that last walk of his to die in the fields he used to till” [1]. Are we humans really Gurdianless now? Is not there any Allah waiting for us? Davil was happy that he will be thrown into hellfire by God, but Devil will be nihilist now because no Allah will be there to punish him any longer. He would perhaps just stare at nothingness forever. This is perhaps more terrible pain for Davil.

4. Conclusion

It is clear that the Islamic worldview provides the meaning of human life that is completely associated with Allah’s purpose of worshipping him as sole creator. On the other hand, the scientific worldview completely rejects any sort of religious teaching on the topic of giving meaning of life. Every religious belief is negated by proponents of scientific worldview. Religious teaching has nothing to do with natural truth that the universe is presenting us with empirical pieces of evidence. That is the major clash between the scientific worldview and the Islamic worldview. Why am I here? What is the purpose of our life? What is the meaning of life? All these philosophical questions we do ask at one point in our life despite it is not necessary for living in daily lives, yet those are the questions that are associated from generation to generation. In 20th and 21st centuries, scientific worldview tries to answer those questions that were usually dealt by theologians or philosophers at the past.

In Bengali, I had favourite song that is deeply associated with Islamic worldview and scientific worldview. Not sure if the writer Mizanur Rahman Raihan was aware of the trend of scientific worldview:

Oi Chader Alo Aj Lagena Valo Keno Jani Na
Tumi Sara Ei Shundor Prithibi Mani Na

[Translation: Not sure the moonlight no longer attracts me today

Without you (oh God!) I would never subscribe the beauty of this Universe]

Unfortunately weather we ever subscribe the beauty of universe or not, this universe simply does not care anyone’s existence as scientific worldview presented upon us. How do we, as Muslim youths, overcome this crisis? By simply trying to act as ignorant of the facts of scientific data and their highly prediction or by using post-modern thought of relativity of truth? Thousands of predictions can be wrong. We do have in our mind. Yet the skepticism never goes away due to the influence of the scientific worldview.

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